

Collecting: Possession or Meaning?

Or, why do we collect if one day everything will be lost?

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Collecting is something that has always intrigued me. We often see it as a mere act of consumption, but I like to think of it as an assignment of meaning. A stubborn attempt to write stories through items or objects.

This thought became more present a few years ago when I started playing *Star Trek Timelines*. The game currently (in 2025) has over 1,700 characters, and there are people who *have* (for lack of a better word) more than 1,600 in their accounts. I have around 700. The community website, datacore.app, did some crazy calculations and said that if I continue playing normally, it should take me another 10 years to complete my collection. This is obviously a lie, because some characters have already been removed from the game. And one day, when the game ends, the servers will be shut down, and I will lose my entire collection. And that's why I ask myself: why dedicate so much effort to something destined to disappear?

To explore this question, I want to quickly compare two very different collections.

Many years ago, I had a very strange collection: defective matchsticks. It wasn't very large, about 20 of them, kept in a similarly defective matchbox. Twenty may not seem like much, but

each one I found was a unique victory. Double-headed matchsticks were the most common, and sometimes I would replace one with an even stranger find. But try to imagine 20 different types of defects. It isn't easy.

The other collection is a bit more common: Funko Pops. This type of collection needs no introduction, as many people own dozens of these figures. I only have one, so perhaps I have the smallest Funko collection in the world. It's the Cigarette Smoking Man from *The X-Files*, my favorite character from the series. Unlike my matchsticks, these objects are made to be collected. Some are released in limited editions precisely to increase their value. Others, poor things, are buried "alive," left to pollute the planet and, in turn, increase the value of the remaining ones. I should mention that I know the debate about the figures buried in the Arizona landfill is controversial: the manufacturer claims it was just surplus inventory, while collectors swear it was done to inflate the value of those that remained.

I find it interesting to compare these two collections because one is likely the negation of the other. While the defective matchsticks are industrial accidents, since no one produced them to be collected, Funkos are mass-produced to be desired and, eventually, discarded. These matchsticks are a kind of involuntary ready-made, a unique and rare piece. The figures, however, are prized for their quantity: the more you have, or the rarer they are, the greater the collector's standing in the community (at this point, the collection and the collector merge). Finding a defective matchstick is a kind of natural lottery; it's hard to find, and besides luck, you need a keen eye to prevent a specimen from slipping through your fingers. Funkos can be found with some luck in specialty stores or at gaming events, or easily purchased on websites. Finally, there's a psychological durability; many Funko collections may only last until the next trend.

I like to think of my lost matchstick collection as an anti-collection. Or perhaps it was the opposite: an example of conscious collecting. In it, I wasn't a consumer, but a sort of curator of chance, someone who keeps what the world rejects. It is at this point that Funkos present me with a challenge. The wall of consumerism surrounding them is massive, and I had trouble seeing past it. This unease led me to wonder if what I was feeling wasn't, in fact, an echo of much deeper, universal motivations that all of us collectors share.

Some collect for nostalgia. This includes those who keep childhood toys or vinyl records that harken back to a time that will never return. Others seek order and control in a chaotic world: organizing, cataloguing, and completing a set becomes as important, if not more so, than the collection itself. There are also those who collect for status, displaying rarities like trophies on shelves or in gaming profiles. And finally, there are the dopamine addicts, who just want that thrill of unboxing a new item, whether it's a sealed Funko Pop or a legendary character in *Star Trek Timelines*.

There is even an acronym for these five invisible forces, TOMOS: Tribe, to belong to a group, of collectors, for example; Organization, to impose order on chaos; Memory, to freeze time; Objective, to complete something like lists and wishes; and Status, to be recognized. To this, add FOMO (Fear of Missing Out), driven by limited-edition objects or virtual items from seasonal events, like Christmas 2024. This factor gives gamers and other collectors an extra motivation to acquire certain items at specific times, or else they will be without them.

But even with all these explanations, the initial question remains: if everything will be lost, why do we do it?

The answer, for me, lies in the meaning of each of these collections. My defective matchsticks were silent messages. They told me to look at what no one else sees, that these victories of the excluded are more important than the monotony of perfection, and that together they told a story of industries, defects, and chance. My lone Funko among my books shouts, "This character intrigues me!" My *Star Trek Timelines* characters freeze moments from my childhood and adolescence, from watching *The Original Series* in black and white to the speed and irreverence of *Lower Decks*. More than that, they tell a story of achievement, of how I got a character like Locutus of Borg after years of playing, the thrill of finally getting him, the screenshot on Discord for my fellow players to see my accomplishment.

One day, all of this will be lost. Yes. The matchsticks are long gone, my Funko is an ocean away from me, and my Locutus will one day be erased from the servers.

That is why what matters least in a collection are its items. Collecting is just a way of giving meaning to the fleeting. What remains are not the objects, but the experience of having brought them together. Our achievements, frustrations, and the marks this journey leaves on us. We invest our time, money, and effort for a moment of satisfaction, and a story that becomes eternal.

And you, what story does your collection tell about you?